

ANALYSIS OF EFFECTIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural
Mechanization Engineers, National
Research University, English department
teacher **Usmanova Dilbar**

Abstract. Teaching English is an important aspect of education in the world today. For effective learning, students need to use methods that allow them to master the language quickly and effectively. In this article, we will look at various methods of teaching English and analyze their effectiveness.

Keywords: language, English language, method, non-philological direction, technology, teaching, education.

Nowadays, one of the most important issues in education is the purpose, content, methods, tools, organizational forms, imparting knowledge and realizing the educational goal based on the subject material studied in the course of education.

at this paper, we will consider the methodological features of teaching English at non-physical universities. Turn to the methodology and express your point of view on the theoretical foundations of teaching a foreign language for specific purposes. Modern linguistics encompasses linguistics, linguistics, psychology, cognitive linguistics, ethnolinguistics, discourse analysis, and the creation of new languages.

There are many methods of teaching English, and the effectiveness of each of them depends on the individual characteristics of the students. However, there are some common approaches that are often recognized as effective methods of teaching English:

- **Communicative approach:** the emphasis is on the development of oral speech and the ability to communicate in English. Lessons are built around real-life

communication situations, which helps students learn the language faster and easier.

- **The methodology of game learning:** the use of games and entertainment tasks for learning English contributes to more effective memorization of material and increased motivation of students.
- **Using technology:** interactive training programs, online courses, video tutorials and other technical tools help to make the learning process more interesting and accessible.
- **Personalized approach:** taking into account the individual needs and capabilities of each student allows you to create a more effective learning environment.
- **Regular practice:** constant repetition of the material, carrying out various practical tasks and homework helps to consolidate knowledge and skills.

Of course, the choice of teaching methods should depend on the learning goals, age and level of knowledge of students, so it is important to choose the appropriate method or combination of them to achieve the best results in learning English.

One of the most effective methods of teaching English is the method of communicative learning. This method focuses on the development of students' oral speech, as well as the ability to understand and use language in real communication situations. Students are offered the maximum amount of time to practice communication in English, which contributes to their rapid progress.

Another effective method of teaching English is the feedback method. When using this method, the teacher actively communicates with students, helping them correct mistakes and improve their language proficiency. Such an individual approach helps students to improve their skills faster and achieve the desired results.

It is also necessary to take into account the different types of teaching materials when teaching English. The use of a variety of textbooks, audio and video materials, as well as interactive online resources can significantly improve students' language acquisition. This will help them develop all aspects of the language - grammar, vocabulary, written and spoken language.

In conclusion, effective teaching of English requires the use of a variety of methods that contribute to the rapid and high-quality assimilation of the material by students. A communicative approach, a feedback method and the use of a variety of teaching materials are just a few of the methods that can be used to achieve successful results in teaching English.

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